

practice, and 3.9-8.7 t/ha for improved practice, largely reflecting site fertility (see table). The low IR36 yields at some sites was attributed to severe weed pressure, low soil fertility where farmers applied no FYM, and prolonged water stress at tillering and flowering.

The grain yield increase obtained with IR36 was economically attractive. The

marginal benefit-cost ratio (MBCR) was estimated at 5.3 with local practice and 6.8 with improved practice (see table).

The data indicate that, with better management and on more fertile sites, short-statured IR36 could produce as much straw as the local varieties (11-19 t/ha), but that under average conditions straw productivity may be

inferior.

IR36 has the potential for high yield in the valley; however, its susceptibility to drought, lack of cold tolerance at the reproductive phase (important where rather late planting is common), and seemingly inadequate straw production preclude its wide promotion. □

DAK83 – a promising new aromatic selection for small holders in Tanzania

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Rice in Tanzania is grown predominantly by subsistence farmers. Their acceptance of a variety is determined mainly by its cooking and eating qualities. Supa India, with excellent grain quality, is widely grown, although it has several agronomic deficiencies.

A breeding program to develop an improved variety with high yield potential and acceptable grain quality was initiated at DARC in 1982. Crosses were made between Supa and elite pedigree lines that were derivatives of Supa crosses made in Zanzibar. Several selections possessing intermediate plant type, earliness, and aromatic, long to medium-slender grains were isolated.

DAK83-99-27-3 (DAK83) is a pregony selection from Supa India/ Line 302D (selected pedigree line from BKN6820/Supa India). It has intermediate aroma, high yield potential, and short growth duration. It was further tested in yield trials at four sites during 1985 and 1986 wet and dry seasons (see table). It yielded 3.6-7.5 t/ha, with an average of 5.2 t/ha – higher by 1.7 t/ha than the average yield of Supa.

DAK83 has average plant height of 106 cm with no tendency to lodge even at 120 kg N/ha. It matures almost a month earlier (110 d) than Supa (135+ d), and more uniformly. Its

Grain yield of DAK83 in different trials at 4 sites in Tanzania, 1985-86.

Location	Entries tested (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Rank of DAK83
		Highest	DAK83	Lowest	Check ^a	
<i>1985 wet season</i>						
Dakawa	6	7.7	5.6	4.2	4.2 (IR579)	2
Dakawa	15	9.4	7.5	3.1	6.1 (Katrin)	3
Dakawa	5	4.7	3.6	2.5	2.5 (Katrin)	3
<i>1985 dry season</i>						
Dakawa ^{b9}	5.6	1.8 ^c		1.4	3.3 (Katrin)	7
<i>1986 wet season</i>						
Dakawa	5	6.2	5.3	5.0	5.1 (IR579)	2
Dakawa	15	7.1	5.0	4.5	3.5 (Supa)	5
Dakawa	30	5.8	4.7	2.8	3.9 (IR60)	6
Mbeya-Igurusi	9	7.9	4.8	3.0	3.8 (Kahogo)	6
Tabora-Mwamapuli	6	4.4	4.1	1.5	1.5 (Supa)	2
DRF-Farms	6	5.5	4.2	3.3	3.9 (IRE)	2

^aCheck variety names in parentheses. ^bIrrigated. ^c60% bird damage.

cooking and eating qualities are not significantly different from those of Supa. Farmers' acceptance of DAK83 is

higher than that for newly released nonaromatic cultivars. □

CR314-5-10: a promising culture for shallow rainfed lands of the Chhotanagpur plateau region of Bihar

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Chhotanagpur has 1.23 million ha under rice cultivation in wet season; of this, 4% is irrigated and the remaining rainfed. The rainfed area is further classified into dryland (11%), shallow rainfed bunded upland with 0-30 cm water depth (55%), intermediate rainfed with 30-100 cm water depth (27%) and deepwater with

Table 1. Performance of CR314-5-10 and check variety Ratna under direct seeded conditions at Hazaribag and Kanke, Bihar, India, 1984-85.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering		Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Hazaribag	Kanke	Hazaribag		Kanke 1984
			1984	1985	
CR314-5-10	89	93	3.8	2.7	4.2
Ratna	91	94	2.7	2.0	2.6
LSD (P = 0.05)			0.6	0.3	0.8
Increase (%) over Ratna			40		60

100 cm or more (3%). Rice cultivar CR314-5-10, developed at CRURRS, was identified as the most promising culture for the bunded uplands.

CR314-5-10 derived from IR42/IR5853-118-5, is a semidwarf culture with stiff straw and takes about 115 d to mature. It has good early vigor, allowing proper stand establishment and competition with weeds. It possesses a fair degree of tolerance for drought in the vegetative phase and has long panicles (27.5 cm). Grains are long and slender (length:width = 3.2) with white kernels; 1,000-grain weight is 24.0 g.

CR314-5-10 was evaluated under direct seeded conditions in station trials and under transplanted conditions in all India Coordinated trials from 1983 to 1985. In station trials it produced significantly higher average yields than check variety Ratna over a 2-yr period

Table 2. Performance of CR314-5-10 in multilocal trials under transplanted conditions, Bihar, India, 1983-85.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Panicles (m ²)	Average yield ^a (t/ha)				
			Wet season		Dry season		
			1983 (20)	1984 (22)	1984 (6)	1985 (6)	
CR314-5-10	94	288	3.9	3.4	4.3	4.2	
Rasi	83	304	2.8	2.9	4.1	3.5	
IR36	94	320	3.6	3.2	4.4	4.0	
Increase (96)							
Over Rasi ^b					19		
Over IR36 ^b					4		

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the number of sites. ^bBased on mean of 4 seasons.

at Hazaribag and Kanke (Table 1). In the coordinated trials CR314-5-10 showed yield superiority to IR36 and Rasi (Table 2).

CR314-5-10 performed well under the lab-to-land program and was acceptable

to farmers. On the basis of its superiority in grain yield to the check varieties, coupled with its tolerance for drought and blast disease, it has the potential to replace Ratna and Rasi in the Chhotanagpur plateau. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Effect of hydrocortisone on germination of rice

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Hydrocortisone, a steroid hormone of higher animals, promotes cellular activity by influencing carbohydrate and protein metabolism. We studied its effect on germination and growth of rice seedlings.

Seeds of IR50 were soaked in 0, 50, 100, 200, and 500 ppm concentrations of hydrocortisone solution for 6 or 24 h. Germination increased up to 100 ppm with 6 h soaking (see table). Soaking for 24 h improved germination more than 6 h soaking. Root and shoot lengths nearly doubled with 100 ppm hydrocortisone. Hydrocortisone may have promoted cell elongation or multiplication of cells, or both.

Dry matter accumulation decreased with hydrocortisone, probably because

Effect of hydrocortisone on germination and seedling growth. Coimbatore, India.

Hydrocortisone concentration (ppm)	Germination (%)		Root length (cm)		Shoot length (cm)		Seedling dry weight (mg)	
	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h
	0 (control)	60	80	7.13	7.06	3.79	3.07	16.08
50	70	85	7.87	8.28	4.22	3.29	15.25	14.94
100	80	85	14.29	13.76	8.07	7.33	14.90	15.00
200	60	85	6.42	7.89	3.39	3.08	15.25	15.70
500	65	70	6.21	5.85	3.55	2.34	15.23	17.00
CD	11	9	1.46	1.17	1.03	0.76	ns	1.54

of increased utilization of seed reserves. Higher maintenance respiration might also have contributed to lower dry matter accumulation.

Soaking in hydrocortisone for 24 h enhanced root growth but had a more adverse effect on shoot growth than soaking for 6 h. The 500 ppm concentration generally depressed germination and growth, perhaps because of the toxic effect of the chemical.

These findings suggest that hydrocortisone has the potential to increase cellular activities in plants.

Detailed studies on the effect of foliar hydrocortisone sprays at different growth stages on productivity are in progress. □

Genotype × planting system interaction for flowering in rice

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The number of days to flowering or